

Title: FANTASIA leverages language models to decode the functional dark proteome across the Animal Tree of Life

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Abstract

Protein functional annotation is crucial in biology, but many protein-coding genes remain uncharacterized, especially in non-model organisms. FANTASIA (Functional ANnoTation based on embedding space SmilArity) integrates protein language models for large-scale functional annotation. Applied to ~1,000 animal proteomes, FANTASIA predicts functions to virtually all proteins, including up to 50% that remained unannotated by traditional homology-based methods. This enables the discovery of novel gene functions, enhancing our understanding of molecular evolution and organismal biology. FANTASIA holds particular promise for functional discovery in non-model taxa, offering advantages over homology-based tools in sensitivity and generalizability. FANTASIA is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/CBBIO/FANTASIA>.

Introduction

Understanding protein function is essential for deciphering genome evolution and the complexity of life. Gene Ontology (GO) provides a standardized vocabulary to describe gene functions across species¹, organizing terms into three categories: biological process, molecular function, and cellular component. This framework is crucial for interpreting genome-wide data, yet a substantial portion of protein-coding genes, particularly in non-model organisms, but also in model organisms to a lesser extent, remain unannotated, forming what we call the “dark proteome”.

Experimental knowledge of protein function remains extremely limited, with fewer than 0.5% of proteins having been functionally characterized to date². To bridge this gap, traditional annotation methods^{3,4} primarily rely on function transference via sequence similarity, which limits their effectiveness for annotating highly divergent or fast-evolving proteins. Many genes remain undetected or uncharacterized due to rapid evolution, orphan status, or intrinsic disorder, making their functional classification particularly challenging. For example, approximately 30% of proteins in the model organism *Caenorhabditis elegans* lack a functional annotation in UniProt⁵. This problem is even more pronounced in non-model species, where 41% of genes in a tardigrade⁶ and 50% in a sponge⁷ remain unannotated. Moreover, orphan genes, which lack detectable homologs, can comprise up to one-third of predicted genes in eukaryote genomes⁸.

The challenge posed by the dark proteome is particularly pressing, as incomplete or inaccurate functional annotations can lead to biased biological interpretations, impairing enrichment analyses, network inference, and comparative genomics. Poorly characterized genes may also be linked to important evolutionary innovations, and their omission from analyses can result in incomplete or misleading models of evolutionary change, limiting the ability to identify conserved or lineage-specific features. These limitations hinder biological discovery and slow the pace of basic and applied research. The urgency is illustrated by the rapid expansion of genomic data from large-scale initiatives such as the Earth BioGenome Project⁹ and the European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA)^{10,11}. These efforts are generating unprecedented volumes of genomic information, highlighting the critical need for reliable functional annotation frameworks that go beyond conventional sequence-similarity-based approaches.

Incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) techniques has enhanced the performance of prediction methods¹². However, despite the fast evolving pace in this area, there is still room for improvement, especially when applied to full proteomes from unconventional organisms. Further developments benchmarked in CAFA datasets¹², ranging from convolutional neural networks (CNN) deep learning models¹³ to transformer-based protein language models (pLMs)^{2,14}, offer a promising alternative for decoding the 'hidden biology' within the dark proteome. Notably, there is little correlation between pLM-derived embeddings and raw sequence similarity, suggesting that these models capture functional and structural signals beyond traditional homology^{2,14}.

Results and Discussion

FANTASIA: one pipeline to annotate them all

Since available tools that use pLMs are either hard to escalate to complete proteomes, install or customize for benchmarking or testing different models, here, we introduce FANTASIA (*Functional ANnoTation based on embedding space SImilarity*), a flexible pipeline that uses pre-trained pLMs and embedding similarity searches for large-scale functional annotation (Figure 1). FANTASIA is an improved reimplement of the GOPredSim algorithm² focused on its genome-wide implementation and stability from scratch, together with necessary steps for data preprocessing. FANTASIA's zero-shot capabilities, where functional annotation can be

performed without task-specific fine-tuning, represents a significant advancement. By integrating an efficient implementation, parallel computing techniques, and a streamlined workflow, it significantly improves user-friendliness while maintaining its already tested^{2,5} prediction accuracy. First, given an input proteome or query proteins, it computes protein embeddings using different models, like ProtT5¹⁴ or ESM2¹⁵. The list of proteins can be previously filtered by length, or by sequence similarity, to remove identical sequences within the input or close sequences in the references that can influence results during benchmarking. Then, it employs a robust embedding similarity-based approach to infer GO terms, accessing a on-the-fly generated database of embeddings with functional annotations from different GOA versions. Next, it produces functional predictions using the closest hits or distance-based filtering methods to reduce noise and ensure robustness. Additionally, FANTASIA provides a flexible command-line interface, enabling seamless integration into diverse bioinformatics pipelines. See Methods for more details.

Comparison with other methods

We previously benchmarked those methods on model organisms using the two available pLMs (SeqVec and ProtT5)⁵ against two CNN-based models and a sequence profile-based method. We showed that transformers (SeqVec and ProtT5) predict more precise and informative GO terms than CNN-based methods (DeepGO and DeepGO+), and have a higher coverage -proportion of annotated proteins in the proteome- than traditional homology-based methods, making them suitable for large-scale annotation⁵. Our goal in this work, was to assess the feasibility of zero-shot annotation transfer using broadly accessible models. We specifically showed that transformers increased annotation coverage (number of sequences annotated), term inference precision, and informativeness (or detail), while being able to recover accurate functional information from transcriptomic experiments⁵. Since prot-T5 was the best performer in our benchmark, it was selected to expand the analyses to 970 species (~23 million genes) covering the full animal diversity. As non-model organisms lack “ground” annotation standards, it is not possible to conduct a proper benchmark as the previous one.

Nevertheless, repeating some comparative analyses yielded the same results in terms of informativeness (Supp. information and Fig. S1) and annotation coverage, where traditional homology-based methods failed to annotate nearly half of the genes, particularly in less-studied phyla (Fig. 2a, Supp. information and Fig. S2). Moreover, we show that FANTASIA, in agreement with the GOpredsim base method, recovers less GO terms per gene (reducing the noise for downstream analyses, Supplementary Note 3, and Supplementary Figure 3). It also recovers a moderately similar functional annotation to the homology-based one, explained by the discrepancy in the number of terms yielded by each method (Supplementary Note 4, and Supplementary Figure 4), and exhibits minimal differences between using all isoforms (and combining all annotations) or just the longest (Supplementary Note 5, and Supplementary Figure 5). In both methods, gene-level annotations remained highly similar, supporting the common practice of using the longest isoform in evolutionary studies while reducing computational costs.

Revealing the ‘hidden biology’ in the dark proteome across the Animal Tree of Life

To show how FANTASIA can access functionally under-characterised biological information, we performed a per phylum GO enrichment analysis of the genes that were not annotated using homology-based methods. While 34.43% of GO terms were phylum-specific, 48 were common to all phyla (Supplementary Note 6, and Supplementary Figure 6), mainly linked to viral response and immune function, both under adaptive evolution in animals. Newly annotated phylum-specific functions are not restricted to a specific group of functions but span diverse biological roles, including essential animal processes (Supplementary Note, and Supplementary Figure 7). However, per-phylum GO enrichment analyses also revealed functions previously undetected by homology-based approaches, linked to unique biological traits. For instance, tardigrades showed stress-related functions that might help us understand their resilience; Micrognathozoa displayed functions tied to the pharynx and unexpected reproductive terms, hinting at undiscovered males or reproductive genes co-option; and ctenophores had newly annotated neuronal functions, shedding light on their unique nervous system (Figure 2b, Supplementary Note 8, and Supplementary Figure 8).

Virtues and challenges

We have shown that FANTASIA is a powerful annotation tool, capable of uncovering meaningful biological insights from ‘hidden’ biology by interpreting the language of proteins. Its zero-shot prediction capabilities allow for strong generalization across diverse taxa, including those underrepresented during training. By leveraging pre-trained models, FANTASIA also aligns with sustainable AI principles. A key limitation, shared by all transformer-based models, is their sensitivity to sequence length, both computationally and biologically restrictive. To mitigate this, FANTASIA v2 was designed as a modular, scalable, and extensible framework, enabling the easy integration of new models as they emerge. While FANTASIA annotates proteins independently of genome context, its performance may still be affected by low-quality or incomplete input data—an inherent challenge shared with other sequence-based methods.

In the era of genomics, pLMs offer a promising complement to homology-based approaches for inferring gene functions in both model and non-model organisms. Here, we demonstrate how these models can highlight functions that are not captured by conventional annotation methods across animals, and present FANTASIA as a reliable tool for inferring function in the coding region of newly-assembled genomes. After all, important biological functions can be found, even in the ‘darkest’ genes, if one has a way to turn on the light.

Methods

FANTASIA pipeline step-by-step

FANTASIA is a reimplementations of the original GOPredSim algorithm² for functionally annotating full proteomes based on GO term transference from protein embedding similarity. Building on the original method, our pipeline enhances usability by offering scalability to full

proteomes, a more reliable installation process with minimized dependency conflicts, and an intuitive command line interface that simplifies parameter customization to facilitate usability. We provide two implementations of FANTASIA to accommodate different user needs. The first, FANTASIA v1, packaged within a Singularity container, was designed for a rapid and straightforward use when unconventional organisms (absent in GOA reference). This version, presented challenges with dependency management. Based on user feedback, which also suggested increase flexibility to accommodate benchmarking approaches and more models, we developed a second version (FANTASIA v2) that uses a vector database for improved stability, traceability and ease of deployment. The full list of differences between both versions is explained in the Supplementary Note 9.

The FANTASIA pipeline consists mainly of five steps: input preprocessing, protein embeddings computation, calculation of embedding similarity against an embedding reference database that contains functional annotations (the Gene Ontology Annotation database), GO terms transference from closest reference sequences embeddings, and output file formatting (Figure 1).

Step 1: Input file preprocessing

FANTASIA allows the removal of long sequences and the application of a sequence similarity filtering¹⁷⁻¹⁹. In FANTASIA v1, this preprocess is mandatory, ensuring that the pipeline can run smoothly by removing identical sequences in the input file and filtering out sequences longer than 5,000 amino acids. In contrast, FANTASIA v2 makes these steps optional and more flexible, allowing users to define maximum length and set a minimum sequence identity threshold (maximum redundancy allowed is 50%). Unlike FANTASIA v1, the sequence similarity filter in FANTASIA v2 is conducted against the annotated reference database using mmseq2¹⁹, and is only recommended for benchmarking purposes (e.g., to evaluate performance on mouse proteins, mouse or closely related sequences must be excluded from the look-up table). For functional annotation of non-model organisms, we do not recommend filtering the look-up table, as retaining as much reference information as possible improves annotation coverage. Input sequence redundancy (not included in FANTASIA v2) can be reduced to save computation time, but this does not impact the method, as annotations are generated per protein. If the minimum sequence identity filter is enabled, FANTASIA v2 concatenates the input dataset with the reference table before computing distances between embeddings (step 3 below). Then, for each query embedding, a comparison is performed against the entire reference table. During this process, embeddings corresponding to sequences that belong to the same cluster as the query are excluded, ensuring that no matches (hits) are made with proteins that exceed the specified sequence identity threshold.

On the other hand, long sequences pose both computational and biological challenges. Transformer models scale poorly with length, often requiring splitting, which can disrupt long-range interaction signals. Biologically, key features like domain boundaries or interaction sites may span across fragments, leading to diluted or misrepresented functional signals. Thus, while splitting long proteins may be necessary, it can compromise representation integrity and

annotation accuracy. UniProtKB excludes sequences over 12,000 residues for embedding generation due to GPU limitations, affecting only a small number of proteins (<https://www.uniprot.org/help/embeddings>). The same is true for FANTASIA v1, where the upper limit of 5,000 in length reduces the computational resources needed, while avoiding issues derived with the embedding interpretation for the SeqVec model we tested in our previous benchmark⁵, which we did not finally include in any of the current versions due to its lower performance.

Step 2: Embedding computation

FANTASIA computes the protein embeddings per model and per sequence, so it is agnostic to the proteome size. FANTASIA v1 only supports ProtT5¹⁴ (Rostlab/prot_t5_xl_uniref50, best model previously benchmarked in ⁵) and uses bioembeddings, while FANTASIA v2 also supports ESM2 (facebook/esm2_t6_8M_UR50D)¹⁵ and ProstT5 (Rostlab/ProstT5)²⁰ to enable addressing of different questions. Although ESM2_t6_8M_UR50D is known to capture evolutionary relationships across species, it has been trained on relatively small datasets. On the other hand, Prot-T5, being trained in the Big Fantastic Database (BFD)¹⁴ excels in handling highly variable sequences or proteins with complex domain structures and provides zero-shot capabilities. ProstT5, as a fine-tuned model, is very useful to address protein structure information. Since bioembeddings triggers many dependencies, the calculation of embeddings in FANTASIA v2 is implemented as in (<https://huggingface.co/>). In both cases, embeddings are stored in HDF5 format for further use. As in the original GOPredSim method, we used the final hidden layer of each model and applied mean pooling over the sequence dimension to obtain the protein-level embeddings.

Step 3: Embedding similarity

FANTASIA then computes the distance between each input sequence embedding (query) and the embeddings in the reference database (look-up table). The reference database in FANTASIA contains, for each reference protein, its pre-computed embeddings for the supported pLMs, and the GO term as in GOA, annotations that will be transferred in step 4 (see below). In FANTASIA v2, this information is stored as a reference vector database managed with PostgreSQL which also contains, for each reference protein, its sequence and metadata for further analyses.

By default, Euclidean distance (d_e) between embeddings n and m for a model with an embedding of embedding size s is computed with the following formula:

$$d_e(n, m) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^s (n_i - m_i)^2}$$

Where s represents the number of dimensions in the embedding space, which varies depending on the selected pLM: $s = 1024$ for ProtT5 and ProstT5, and $s = 320$ for ESM2. These sizes are architectural choices.

Alternatively, FANTASIA v2 allows the selection of cosine similarity (d_c), which is calculated using the formula:

$$d_c(n, m) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^s n_i m_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^s n_i^2} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^s m_i^2}}$$

In FANTASIA v2, batching can be changed, however we keep the original settings to ensure robustness and compatibility with the original use.

In FANTASIA v1, we used Euclidean distance by default to align with the original GOPredSim. In v2, we added support for cosine similarity, which better captures directional similarity and is less sensitive to vector magnitude, an advantage when comparing embeddings across models with different scaling. This allows users to explore alternative distance metrics depending on their annotation needs.

Step 4: GO transference

FANTASIA then transfers GO terms from the k closest embedding-bearing proteins in the database. By default, only the closest hit ($k = 1$) is used. In FANTASIA v2, users can define a distance threshold for each model that determines the maximum allowed distance between query and reference embeddings, which requires user optimization. As reference datasets, FANTASIA v1 uses GO terms from the March 22nd, 2022 release (GOA2022), while FANTASIA v2 uses the current UniprotKB API, (as of March 10th, 2025, UniProtKB uses version 2025 of GOA UniProt. This version was assembled using publicly available data from source databases on March 3, 2025), this guarantees that FANTASIA always use the latest GOA version, although older versions can also be used. Evidence codes are CAFA-recommended experimental evidence codes (e.g., EXP, IDA, IPI, IMP, IGI, IEP, TAS).

Step 5: Output description and formatting

The standard output of FANTASIA gives the user information on the GO terms assigned to each input protein, along with the associated reliability index (see below). In FANTASIA v1, the output is a tab-separated file where each row represents a GO-input protein pair, with columns for the sequence accession, the GO term identifier, and the reliability index. In FANTASIA v2, the output is a comma-separated file (CSV) with 10 columns: 1) sequence accession (header); 2) GO term identifier; 3) GO category (F: molecular function, P: biological process, C: cellular component); 4) GOA evidence code for the reference annotation; 5) GO term description; 6) embedding distance (Euclidean or cosine) between the query and the reference; 7) protein language model used for the embedding generation; 8) UniProt ID of the reference protein bearing the closest embedding; 9) organism the target reference protein belongs to; 10) reliability index. Additional columns provide information regarding the sequence similarity of the query vs. the closest-embedding-bearing reference sequence, as calculated by EMBOSS-based

parasail aligner (<https://github.com/jeffdaily/parasail/blob/master/apps/README.md>). It also provides information about GO term traceability (support, collapsed terms, etc). By default, FANTASIA converts this standard output to the input file format for topGO's GO enrichment¹⁶ to facilitate its application in a wider biological workflow in functional genomics. This feature can be disabled by the user in FANTASIA v2.

The reliability index (RI) was previously established in², and is a transformation of the distance between the query q and hit in the database (q, n_i) into a similarity scale, making it easier to compare between functional annotation results. Supported RI formulations:

For Euclidean distance (d_e), RI is defined using the inverse similarity transformation as:

$$RI = \frac{0.5}{0.5 + d_e(q, n_i)}$$

Where lower Euclidean distances yield higher confidence scores.

For cosine similarity (d_c), RI is computed with the direct similarity measure:

$$RI = 1 - d_c(q, n_i)$$

While both formulations produce values ranging from 0 to 1, they are not directly comparable, as they capture confidence in different ways. Users should exercise caution when interpreting RI scores across different similarity metrics. Additionally, the Euclidean distance is not inherently comparable across different pLMs, as it depends on the magnitude of the embedding vectors generated by each model. In contrast, the cosine similarity metric is more suitable for cross-model comparisons, as it primarily captures the relative orientation of embeddings rather than their absolute magnitude.

Importantly, RI values do not necessarily correlate with prediction accuracy. In model organisms, we observed that true annotations (i.e., exact GO term matches) and biologically relevant functions can still be recovered within the second quantile of the RI distribution⁵. In the context of non-model organisms, where no ground truth is available, RI thresholds cannot be optimized. Therefore, we recommend using RI as a general indicator of high or low support, rather than as a strict measure of accuracy.

FANTASIA can be executed on both GPUs or CPUs, depending on the available hardware, though GPU-based execution is recommended for improved speed (Supplementary Figure 9b). The computational complexity of the pipeline is $O(n)$, where n is the number of sequences in the input dataset. Both versions perform very similarly on their speed (See Supplementary Note 9, and Supplementary Figure 9).

Input datasets and processing

We obtained the proteome files for 961 animals and 9 outgroup species from MATEdb²¹ (Supplementary Data 1). This dataset comprises the longest peptide sequence (or isoform) per

gene, totaling 23,184,398 sequences, derived from high-quality genomes and transcriptomes representing nearly all animal phyla. To assess the impact of annotating all isoforms versus only the longest, we created a subset of 93 species (Supplementary Data 1) to maximize representation across the Animal Tree of Life.

We annotated the functions (assigned GO terms) of the longest and all isoforms datasets using (1) FANTASIA v1 with the ProtT5 model and (2) eggNOG-mapper as a proxy for annotation based on homology. Euclidean distance was selected for consistency with previous benchmarks where it was reported that cosine similarity yielded similar results². We used eggNOG-mapper 2.1.6³ as described in MATEdb2²¹. To ensure comparability, we used the datasets filtered by length and by removal of identical sequences, as provided by FANTASIA v1, as input for eggNOG-mapper. Homology-based results were then filtered to remove the GO terms that have a depth in the GO graph (DAG) lower than 2 (i.e. the terms are very general, close to or at the root of the DAG, and not informative). The difference in annotation coverage between the filtered and unfiltered homology-based annotations is negligible (Supplementary Figure 2, light purple).

When exploring the effect of using all isoforms for functional annotation, we first annotated all isoform sequences and then obtained per-gene annotations by collapsing the annotation of each isoform to retrieve a list of unique GOs.

In addition, we performed an extra RI-based filtering for FANTASIA results (see above for an explanation on RI). Thresholds for filtering were obtained from the source GOPredSim publication² based on evaluations using CAFA3¹²: 0.35 for biological process, 0.28 for molecular function, and 0.29 for cellular component. It should be noted that these values were estimated based on the CAFA3¹² F1 max comparisons datasets which do not necessarily scale to longer and more diverse datasets, as we have previously shown in model organisms⁵ where thresholds require to be optimised.

Information Content

To analyse GO terms according to depth within the GO graph, we estimated their Information Content (IC) using a custom script (https://github.com/cbbio/Compute_IC) which is defined as²²:

$$IC = -\log_2(p(t))$$

Where $p(t)$, the probability of a term occurring in a dataset, is calculated as:

$$p(t) = 1 - \frac{\text{'Offspring Count'}}{\text{'Offspring Count'} + \text{'Ancestors Count'}}$$

Offspring and ancestors count refer to the number of proteins that are assigned to that term given a reference Gene Product Association Data file (GAPD). In this case, the reference GAPD, or universe of proteins, combined all GAPD files for all species available. Higher IC implies a more specific GO term while low IC values means that the GO term is more general.

Semantic similarity

To assess how similar two different annotations are, we obtained the lists of genes that were commonly annotated by both methods for the representative subset of species representing all phyla ($n=93$) and calculated for each gene their semantic similarity between the GO terms inferred independently for each of the 3 GO term categories. To be more conservative in our analysis, we used the most filtered dataset for each method (i.e., filtering by reliability index). We used pygoosemsim (<https://github.com/mojaie/pygoosemsim>) to estimate the Wang semantic similarity²³ between protein-coding gene annotations using the Best-Match Average (BMA) method for gene products annotated with multiple GO terms. Semantic similarity (sim_{BMA}) between 2 gene products ($g1$ and $g2$) is calculated as follows:

$$sim_{BMA}(g1, g2) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} sim(go1i, go2j) + \sum_{j=1}^n \max_{1 \leq i \leq m} sim(go1i, go2j)}{m+n}$$

where m and n are the number of GO terms annotated in $g1$ and $g2$, respectively; and $go1i$ and $go2j$ are the GO term in position i (from 1 to m) from the $g1$ and the GO term in position j (from 1 to n) from the $g2$, respectively. sim_{BMA} Semantic similarity values range from 0 to 1, with 0 meaning no similarity and 1 meaning (almost) identical.

The Wang similarity method, unlike other metrics, is based on the GO DAG topology, making it more stable than others based on information content that rely on the available annotations although it can lead to information loss. However, in the case of non-model organisms, the biological context can be highly variable. In such uncertain settings, we find that Best-Match Average (BMA) offers a balanced compromise: it reduces noise while retaining meaningful, context-relevant information by accounting for multiple matches. Although all similarity aggregation methods (such as maximum or average) have their limitations, BMA provides a practical middle ground when the precise relationship between annotations is unknown.

GO enrichment for genes not annotated by homology-based methods

We obtained the list of genes that were not annotated by homology for each species and performed a GO enrichment analysis using topGO¹⁶ against the whole set of proteins of that species to identify which functions were being missed by homology. We used the GO terms

predicted using FANTASIA. TopGO, in contrast to other GO enrichment methods, is based on the GO DAG, allowing us to take relationships between GO terms into account.

From the GO enrichment per species, we obtained a list of GO terms enriched per phylum by combining the results per species. For that, in the case of GO terms that were enriched in at least one species, we combined the p-values using the ordmeta method²⁴.

We then identified the list of GO terms that were commonly enriched in all animal phyla. Among all common GO terms (Supplementary Table 1), we focused on toxin activity (GO:0090729) to assess the performance of the functional annotation. Among all animals with venom, we selected the scorpion *Centruroides sculpturatus* to look into the genes with this GO term that were not annotated by homology. We used ToxinPred2²⁵ to further filter this list and identified CSCU1_DN0_c0_g23215_i1.p1 (XP_023242874.1, uncharacterized protein) as a putative homolog of tachylectin-5 (XP_023224331.1, 61.20% of sequence similarity). We further assessed this by predicting their structure with ColabFold²⁶ and comparing them with the experimentally-determined structure of the horseshoe crab *Tachypleus tridentatus* tachylectin-5A (PDB 1JC9) using the PDB pairwise structure alignment tool (TM-align)²⁷. These results can be found in S6.

Data visualization

To visualize the significantly enriched GO terms per phylum and GO category, we first calculated the Wang semantic similarity matrix for each dataset and compared several clustering algorithms using the simplifyEnrichment R package²⁸, and proceeded with the K-means algorithm (Supplementary Data 2). Then, to summarize the function of each cluster, we obtained their representative GO term by selecting the GO term with the lowest closeness value (the 'farthest') in the subset semantic similarity network for that cluster. Results were plotted in a TreeMap (Supplementary Data 3).

We then combined the results of all phyla by assigning each significant GO term to the GO slim AGR (Alliance of Genomics Resources) subset using the map-to-slim.py script available in GOAtools²⁹. Between 10 and 60% of GO terms per phylum were not assigned to a category and were further clustered as explained above. The GO representative terms of each of the 49 clusters were later manually assigned to the GO slim AGR classification and used to include unassigned GOs in the GO-GO category list. Final results were normalized per phylum (row) and visualized in a heatmap.

Statistics and Reproducibility

Statistical significance for GO enrichment was assessed using the elim algorithm in the topGO¹⁶ package, which accounts for the hierarchical structure of the GO graph. An alpha threshold of 0.05 was applied to identify significant terms. Because elim computes p-values conditioned on the structure of neighboring GO terms, and GO terms are, therefore, not independent, multiple testing is not applicable. Enrichment results across species were aggregated at the phylum level

by combining independent p-values using the ordmeta method²⁴, a meta-analysis approach based on the joint distribution of ordered p-values.

GO knowledgebase is regularly updated with new releases that remove obsolete GO terms or add new ones, changing in addition the structure of the graph, which hinders comparison between analyses that use different versions³⁰. Hence, to ensure consistency and comparability, we used the same Gene Ontology (GO) release version across analyses whenever possible. Specifically, we used GOA2022 (March 22, 2022) for all FANTASIA v1 annotations and GOslim subsets, and the June 11, 2023 release for information content and semantic similarity analyses.

Computational resources

FANTASIA was tested in several computing environments. The performance of FANTASIA v1 was assessed in the Finisterrae III HPC (FT3, Centro de Supercomputación de Galicia, CESGA) using CPU nodes, and NVIDIA A100 GPU nodes with 32 CPUs per node and a maximum of 250 GB RAM, CUDA version 11.0. FANTASIA v2 was evaluated on (1) a desktop workstation at CBBIO lab with an AMD Ryzen 9 5950X 16-core processor CPU (128 GB RAM), and a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 Ti GPU (24 GB VRAM), CUDA version: 12.4; and (2) an HPC with NVIDIA A100-SXM4-80GB with CUDA 12.1, utilizing a single GPU, 50 CPU cores, and 100 GB of RAM. Animal proteomes GO annotations were performed in DragoHPC cluster (Spanish National Research Council, CSIC) using nodes with an NVIDIA Ampere A100 graphic card with 512 GB and Dual Intel Xeon Gold 6248R 24C 3.0GHz processors. Only one species (*Panulirus ornatus*) was annotated using CPUs in FT3 due to the limitation in the maximum GPU nodes RAM memory.

Data availability

All proteomes, homology-based annotations and FANTASIA.V1 (ProtT5 per-protein embeddings and annotations) are available in MATEdb²¹. Information content, semantic similarity and other results are provided in Zenodo³¹⁻³⁶. The complete list of the Zenodo files, as well as the Supplementary Data 1-4 can be found on GitHub (https://github.com/MetazoaPhylogenomicsLab/Martinez_Redondo_et_al_2024_Dark_Proteome_Animal_Tree_Of_Life).

Code availability

Both versions are functional and available. FANTASIA v1 pipeline used for the supplementary analyses is included in a Singularity (v3.8.3+231-g9dceb4240) container available on GitHub (<https://github.com/MetazoaPhylogenomicsLab/FANTASIA>). FANTASIA v2 pipeline is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/CBBIO/FANTASIA>). Steps followed for the creation of several intermediate files not available on Zenodo, as well as additional scripts used for the analyses and creating figures are available on GitHub (https://github.com/MetazoaPhylogenomicsLab/Martinez_Redondo_et_al_2024_Dark_Proteome_Animal_Tree_Of_Life).

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Author contributions

GIMR, AMR and RF designed the study. GIMR performed the main analyses, created the FANTASIA v1 singularity container, and designed the figures. GIMR and IB wrote the original FANTASIA code and the pipeline to automate the methods. FMPC developed the FANTASIA v2 implementation. IC, and JMF optimized development, documentation, and extensively tested the tool and conducted statistics. BC and MVV assisted with data analysis. GIMR, AMR and RF wrote the first version of the manuscript. RF and AMR provided resources, the rationale and concepts behind the work, and supervised the study. All authors revised and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Figures

Figure 1. FANTASIA pipeline overview. Input proteomes are preprocessed to remove sequences based on length and sequence similarity if needed. Then, embeddings are computed, and distance embedding similarity is calculated against the reference database (using two metrics at will). Optionally, it converts the standard GOPredSim output file to the input file format for topGO¹⁶ to facilitate its application in a wider biological workflow.

